

COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY FOR DIAGNOSING SPLENIC DISORDERS

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Objective: To evaluate the capabilities and effectiveness of CT imaging in the diagnosis of mechanical spleen injuries, as well as various non-traumatic splenic masses.

Materials and Methods: An analysis was conducted on the results of CT scans from 62 patients with suspected traumatic and non-traumatic spleen abnormalities between January 2022 and December 2024.

Results and Discussion: The age of the patients ranged from 30 to 75 years, with the majority being male (65%). Diagnostic conclusions were confirmed either intraoperatively or clinically (in cases of conservative management). The incidence of identified pathological changes was distributed as follows: ruptures of the spleen parenchyma and capsule, infarctions (30%), subcapsular hematomas (14%), various cysts (9%), chronic and acute abscesses (6%), metastatic lesions (5% of cases), and hemangiomas (3%). The sensitivity and specificity of CT with intravenous bolus contrast in diagnosing spleen injuries were 100%, with no false-negative or false-positive results. For non-traumatic changes, the sensitivity and specificity of the method varied between 92% and 96%, depending on the type of pathology. Following CT, the diagnosis was revised in 12% of patients, and treatment strategy was adjusted in 32% of cases.

Conclusions: The use of CT with intravenous bolus contrast in patients with traumatic and non-traumatic splenic lesions allows for high-precision determination of the nature of detected pathologies. It facilitates the selection of an appropriate treatment strategy, helps avoid unnecessary splenectomies, and accurately identifies the source of bleeding.

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